

Research

Kinematics Analysis and Verification of Six-DoF Humanoid Robotic Manipulator

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Accepted: 20 November, 2019; Online: 26 November, 2019

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3554579>

Abstract: The joint coordinate system of the six-degree-of-freedom manipulator is established, and the kinematics equation of the six-degree-of-freedom manipulator is established according to the D-H parameter method. Forward kinematics finds the position and attitude of the end mechanism based on the joint angle of the joint. Inverse kinematics uses geometry methods to solve according to the selections. Using MATLAB to compare the forward and inverse kinematics solution is multiple poses to verify the accuracy of the algorithm and choose the last frame six with the origin at the center of the end-effector flange.

Keywords: six-axis UR5 robot, forward and inverse kinematics, geometry method, MATLAB.

I. Introduction

Robots are traditionally used in industrial automation. In recent years, many robotics researchers have focused on developing humanoid robots [1]. Humanoid robots offer great potential for assisting humans with a variety of tasks. Compared with the traditional industrial robots, the humanoid robot must be able to cope with the wide range of functions and objects encountered in dynamics unstructured environments. As a result, the manipulator of the humanoid robot should be mobility, flexibility, and anthropomorphic for better adaption to typical human environments and to allow for human-like behavior strategies in solving complex tasks [2]. In this method, the initial and final positions and orientations of the end-effector are given, and these represent the manipulators pose to pick or release an object. The algorithm generates intermediate points between the current position and the goal position of the manipulator if required. Then the path is designed using a cubic polynomial

profile to fit the current position, the goal position, and the intermediate points without stopping at every point. To avoid hitting an obstacle, intermediate points are defined such that these reside outside the obstacle sphere boundary. For the development of a robotic system based on the universal robotics arms, researchers require to have access to precise mathematical and simulation models of the UR robots. Such models are essential for motion planning [3, 4], position and force control system design [5, 6].

Nowadays, an essential concern of society is elderly and disabled care. Carrying or moving objects from one place to another are some of the challenging tasks forced by the elderly, who may have also suffered from pain or partial absence of movement in their limbs. Nowadays, robotics appears as a suitable technology that can be implemented to perform some of these tasks. To move an object from one place to another using mobile robot navigation of the robot and motion of its manipulator is required. This research as part of a major project, is focused on the motion of a six-degree-of-freedom (6 DoF) robot manipulator attached to a vacuum compressor and laser printing machine. Forward kinematics can be considered as a mapping from the joint space to the operational space. Any configuration in the joint space can find a unique solution in the operational space. However, different configurations in the joint space may have the same solution in the operational space. Usually, forward kinematics is solved by building a D-H model. Inverse kinematics is a mapping from the operational space to the joint space so that it can be considered as an inverse of forward kinematics because of the complexity of inverse kinematics.

It is usually more complicated than forward kinematics to find the solutions. Therefore, many researchers developed some different approaches for inverse kinematics. In general, those approaches can be divided into four classes namely, the closed-form approach, the numeric approach, the neural network-based approach, and the fuzzy-based approach.

In this paper, the kinematics of a six-degree-of-freedom humanoid robot manipulator is studied. To separate joint variables from the kinematics equation. The rest of the article is organized as follows. In section II, the manipulator architecture of the humanoid robot is represented. The detailed analysis of the kinematics of the manipulator and simulation result is given in sections III, IV, and V., respectively. Finally, the paper ends with a summary and conclusions.

II. The architecture of the six-DoF humanoid robot manipulator

According to the author's research, currently, there are no complete mathematical models for the UR5 robot that could be publicly and readily accessible for MATLAB or any other environment. Researchers developed different models for UR5 robot from scratch [7-25]. Development UR5, Fig 1, is a well-known six-degree-of-freedom robotic manipulator manufactured by Universal Robots Company [26]. The most notable feature of this robot is its agility due to its lightweight, speed, easy to program, flexibility, and safety. One of the main characteristics of the UR5 is that the last three joints of it do not act as a coincidental

wrist. Therefore, all its six joints contribute to the transformational and rotational movements of its end-effector. This characteristic makes the kinematics analysis more complicated in comparison with other manipulators with the coincidental wrist.

Figure 2: Architecture of the UR5 robot manipulator [20].

As was mentioned earlier, currently, there is no complete set of MATLAB models for this robot. Therefore we tried to fill this gap. To achieve this goal, we searched and used the most valid parameters and measurements of UR5 parameters that are used for the development of the models in this paper [25] [26]. The more precise the model, the more valuable and accurate results could be obtained from those models.

Figure 1: The real UR5 manipulator.

III. Kinematics of the humanoid robot manipulator

The schematics of the robotic arm and the allocation of each joint frame illustrated in Fig 2. It is mentioned that the D-H parameters and rotation matrices that are used for the kinematic model are based on these frames. The D-H parameters of the UR5 [27] [28], for the specified joint frames in Fig 2, are presented in Table I.

i	α_i	a_i	d_i	θ_i
1	$\pi/2$	0	$d_1 = 89.2$	$\theta_1 = \pi/2$
2	0	$a_2 = 425$	0	$\theta_2 = \pi/2$
3	0	$a_3 = 392$	0	$\theta_3 = 0$
4	$\pi/2$	0	$d_4 = 109.3$	$\theta_4 = \pi/2$
5	$-\pi/2$	0	$d_5 = 94.75$	$\theta_5 = 0$
6	0	0	$d_6 = 82.5$	$\theta_6 = 0$

Table 1: DH parameters of the UR5 robot arm.

IV. Forward kinematics

Using the definition of the transformation matrix of robotic arms form [22], [23], the transformation matrix from the base to the end effector is in the form of:

$${}^0T_n = \begin{bmatrix} n_x & o_x & a_x p_x \\ n_y & o_y & a_y p_y \\ n_z & o_z & a_z p_z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Then the forward kinematics of the robot position would easily obtain from the fourth column of the T in 1 as:

$$\begin{aligned} p_x &= d_5 c_1 s_{234} + d_4 s_1 - d_6 c_1 c_{234} + a_2 c_1 c_2 + d_6 c_5 s_1 + a_3 c_1 c_2 c_3 - a_3 c_1 s_2 s_3 \\ p_y &= d_5 s_1 s_{234} - d_4 c_1 - d_6 s_1 c_{234} - d_6 c_1 c_5 + a_2 c_2 s_1 + a_3 c_2 c_3 s_1 - a_3 c_1 s_2 s_3 \\ p_z &= d_1 - d_6 s_{234} s_5 + a_3 s_{23} + a_2 s_2 - d_5 c_{234} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where, s_{234} represents the $\sin(\theta_2 + \theta_3 + \theta_4)$ and c_{234} represents $\cos(\cdot)$ of the same.

V. Inverse kinematics

For inverse kinematics, we will find the set joint configuration $Q = q_i$ where $q_i = [\theta_1^i, \dots, \theta_6^i]^T \in [0, 2\pi]^6$ such that satisfies one which describes the desired position and orientation of the last link. Derivation of the inverse kinematics in this section is adopted from [24, 27].

First, finding θ_1 using the position of the 5th joint. Analyzing the transformation from frame 1 to frame 5 using equation 1, this result:

$$-s_1(p_x - d_6 z_x) + c_1(p_y - d_6 z_y) = -d_4$$

That is known as a phase-shift equation whose solution considering Fig. 3 can be found as:

$$\begin{aligned} \tan a_1 &= \frac{0p_{5y}}{0p_{5x}} \\ \tan a_2 &= \frac{d_4}{R} = \frac{d_4}{\sqrt{0p_{5x}^2 + 0p_{5y}^2}} \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\theta_1 = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \frac{\pi}{2} = \text{atan2}(0_{p_{5y}}, 0_{p_{5x}}) \pm \cos^{-1} \frac{d_4}{R} + \pi/2 \quad (3)$$

Figure 3: Geometry of finding θ_1 .

There exist two solutions for θ_1 , where the shoulder is 'left' or 'right.' Using the function $a \tan 2$ is essential for ensuring correct signs and behavior when $0_{p_{5x}} = 0$. In Fig.3, It is easy to see that physically, no configuration is possible which makes $\sqrt{0_{p_{5x}}^2 + 0_{p_{5y}}^2} \leq |d_4| < 0$. Thus, both α_1 and α_2 always exist if an inverse solution exists.

Given a particular, we can solve for θ_1 , we can solve for θ_5 . Using the transformation from frame 1 to frame 6, we can form the below equality.

$$[-s_1 \ c_1 \ 0] \begin{bmatrix} p_x \\ p_y \\ p_z \end{bmatrix} = -d_4 - c_5 d_5$$

This results in:

$$\theta_5 = \pm \cos^{-1} p_x s_1 - \frac{p_x s_1 - p_y c_1 - d_4}{d_6} \quad (4)$$

Again, there are two solutions for which correspond to the configuration where the wrist is "in/down" or "out/up."

Figure 4: Geometry of finding θ_5 .

To solve for the 6th joint, we look at the coordinate axis:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -x_x s_1 + x_y c_1 \\ -y_x s_1 + y_y c_1 \\ -z_x s_1 + z_y c_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -C_6 C_5 \\ S_6 S_5 \\ -C_5 \end{bmatrix}$$

As Fig. 5 shows, this equality forms a spherical coordinate expression for the vector where is the azimuthally angle and is the polar angle. The x and y coordinates of this vector from a system which can easily solve as:

$$\theta_6 = a \tan 2 \left(\frac{y_y c_1 - y_x s_1}{s_5}, \frac{x_x c_1 - x_y s_1}{s_5} \right) \quad (5)$$

Figure 5: Geometry of finding θ_6 .

When $s_5 = 0$, we know $c_5 = \pm 1$, which indicates that the joints 2, 3, 4, and 6 all parallel and the solution are undetermined. When this occurs, a desired θ_6 can be supplied to determine the system entirely.

The other three joints can be derived easily, considering that they act as a 3-RRR planer arm. Once the previous three joints found, the location of the base and end-effector of this 3-RRR arm is available, and then these three joints can be solved. There are two possible configurations, “elbow up” or “elbow down.” No solutions exist when the distance to the 4th joint exceeds the sum $[a_2 + a_3]$ or is less than the difference $[a_2 - a_3]$, If $a_2 = a_3$, a singularity exists when $\theta_3 = 0$, making θ_2 arbitrary

VI. Simulation results

Simulations are performed to verify the correctness of the kinematics equations. The end-effector controlled to move from an endpoint (77.71, 607.5, 597.6) finally place the origin of the reference frame (frame 0) at the robot base, and choose the last frame (frame 6) with the origin at the center of the end-effector flange and z_6 axis along the approach direction.

Figure 6: Motion curve of end effector.

During this process, joint angles vary continuously, as described in Fig. 7. Joint angle plots can be divided into three stages, corresponding to three straight line segments along which the end-effector moves. According to these joint angles derived from the inverse kinematics equations, the position of end-effector can be obtained through forward kinematics equations, as described in Fig. 6. From Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, it is evident that the end effector can be controlled to move along the expected path in the workspace, and the kinematic equations are verified simultaneously.

Figure 7: Angle variety curve for all joints

VII. Conclusion

The kinematics of a six-degree-of-freedom humanoid robot manipulator is analyzed in this paper. Geometry transformation methods are put forward by geometry structure and homogeneous transformation; at the same time, kinematics equation is obtained after those mathematical formulas are provided for humanoid robot manipulator control. The kinematics of the humanoid robot manipulator has simulated in the MATLAB key “Robotics toolbox,” and simulation result verifies the effectiveness of the kinematics equation. UR5 is a lightweight robot arm suitable, pick and place cards for laser printing shown in figure 8 along with the help of vacuum compressor.

Figure 8: UR5 manipulator.

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